

ISic2961

I.Sicily inscription 2961

Language

Latin

Type

Unknown

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

07.2006 and checked 30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in 1882 in the area of the in Neapolis

Coordinates

37.075784, 15.275079

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 247

Physical Description

A fragment of a marble plaque

Dimensions

Height 19 cm

Width 14 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Parts of three lines of Latin letters. The left margin is preserved, but appears broken on the other three sides

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. FICIUḡ

2. ORTE

3. E

Apparatus

ORTEC, Mommsen; the final character could be O or C

NIO, Mommsen; the first character is probably an O, followed by two vertical strokes, of which the second leans to the right

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492320
EDCS 23400458

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.8313 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 85

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 384

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2961. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356512>

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014